

Second-generation of Eurocode 4 - Current innovations and future tasks

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ABSTRACT

This paper will present some of the innovations that will be included within the second-generation of Eurocode 4, which is the European standard for the design of composite steel and concrete structures. The three parts of this standard prEN 1994-1-1, prEN 1994-1-2 and prEN 1994-2 were released for the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) Enquiry Ballot in March 2024. As Chair of CEN/TC 250/SC 4 (which is the subcommittee responsible for Eurocode 4), the present author will present the new structure for this standard, together with a review of selected design provisions that address existing technical issues and support current trends in steel construction. An innovative aspect of this standard is the introduction of three new CEN Technical Specifications which provide rules for: double and single skin composite structures; composite dowels; and high-performance composite columns. This paper will conclude with technical issues that were left unresolved by the project teams, which are considered worthy for future research.

Keywords: Eurocode & Codification; Composite Steel Structures

1 INTRODUCTION

Eurocode 4 is the European Standard (EN) for the design of composite steel and concrete structures. This standard has been developed under the responsibility of Technical Committee 250, Subcommittee 4 (CEN/TC 250/SC 4) and currently consists of three parts, *viz.*:

1. EN 1994-1-1, Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings (1).
2. EN 1994-1-2, Part 1-2: General rules – Structural fire design (2).
3. EN 1994-2, Part 2: General rules and rules for bridges (3).

In 2010 the Eurocodes replaced the former national standards within the 34 countries that are members of CEN. They have also been adopted by other countries around the world, including Singapore (4).

Given that work on the second-generation Eurocodes is nearing completion, the author of this paper will present a selection of the changes that will be included within Eurocode 4, as well as highlighting future areas that may benefit from further research.

2 SECOND-GENERATION OF EUROCODE 4

2.1 Second-generation of the structural Eurocodes

Work commenced on the second-generation Eurocodes in 2015 following the development of a work programme by CEN/TC 250, which is responsible for the structural Eurocodes. Specific tasks were undertaken by the existing Subcommittees (SC), Working Groups (WG), or Horizontal

Groups (HG). An organogram of the current structure of CEN/TC 250 is presented in *Fig.1*, which includes the various Chairs, Convenors and Secretaries for the SCs, WGs and HGs.

Fig. 1. CEN/TC 250 Structural Eurocodes organogram (5)

The CEN process is slightly different compared to that adopted in the development of the current ‘first-generation’ EN Eurocodes. An Enquiry (ENQ) draft is first prepared which possesses the prefix ‘prEN’. After a 16-week public enquiry period and associated ballot, the document is updated in response to comments received and the Formal Vote (FV) draft having the prefix ‘FprEN’ is published for ballot over an 8-week period. Should the FprEN reach a particular threshold of votes in favour, the document is published by CEN as an EN Eurocode.

The following three key dates have been agreed by CEN/TC 250:

- Date of availability (DAV), which is the date when the definitive text of an approved EN is distributed to National Standardisation Bodies (NSBs) by CEN: **April 2022 to March 2026.**
- Date of publication (DoP), which is the latest date that an EN has to be implemented at a national level: **September 2027.**
- Date of withdrawal (DoW), which is the latest date for national standards that conflict with a new EN have to be withdrawn: **March 2028.**

CEN members can determine a national strategy for the publication and implementation of second-generation Eurocodes, provided that it is done within overall timeframe established by the DoP and DoW given above. For example, it has been decided in the UK to publish the EN Eurocodes on the DAV, to enable users to prepare for the transition from the first- to second-generation.

2.2 Eurocode 4

The second-generation of Eurocode 4 will consist of six documents, as follows:

- prEN 1994-1-1, Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings (6).
- prEN 1994-1-2, Part 1-2: Structural fire design (7).
- prEN 1994-2, Part 2: Bridges (8).
- prCEN/TS 1994-1-101: Double and single skin steel concrete composite (SC) structures.
- prCEN/TS 1994-1-102: Design rules for the use of Composite Dowels.
- prCEN/TS 1994-1-103: Design rules for high performance composite columns.

As well as the three new European Technical Specifications (CEN/TSs), to reduce repetition and avoid any ambiguity, it has been decided to remove general rules from prEN 1994-2 and provide cross-references to prEN 1994-1-1. The paper will present a selection of the changes that will be included within the second generation of Eurocode 4, which are summarised within the following sub-sections.

3 GENERAL RULES AND RULES FOR BUILDINGS

3.1 Composite beams with web-openings

Over the last 20-years, many long-span composite systems have been developed which permit mechanical services to be integrated within the structural depth of the floor. A common method of achieving this service integration is by means of openings cut within the webs of composite beams (see *Fig. 2*).

Fig. 2. Cellular beams with elongated openings for integration of mechanical services

prEN 1994-1-1 includes a new Annex, which supports the design of composite beams with web-openings in sagging moment regions and complements the new FprEN 1993-1-13 (9). For cases where the flexural stiffness of the concrete slab above the hole is significant, supplementary design rules are given within a separate Annex, which considers tension in the shear connectors and shear in the concrete.

3.2 Slim floor beams in buildings

Slim floor construction has become popular throughout Europe. The key feature of slim floor construction is the steel beams, which are integrated within the floor depth and possess a wide bottom flange to support the floor slabs. In the UK, slim floor construction has been successfully used in the residential and health sector. It has performed particularly well in vibration sensitive environments such as operating theatres (10), see *Fig. 3*.

Fig. 3. Slimdek® floor for Diagnosis & Treatment Centre at St Richard's Hospital, Chichester, UK

Whilst shallow floor solutions have been adopted widely, they have often been developed as proprietary floor systems in the absence of specific design rules given in Eurocode 4. To remedy this situation, a new annex with generic design rules has been included within prEN 1994-1-1.

4 STRUCTURAL FIRE DESIGN

4.1 Tensile membrane action

Between 1995 and 1996, seven fire tests were undertaken on the eight-storey steel-framed building at the Building Research Establishment (BRE) Large Building Test Facility at Cardington, UK. The tests demonstrated that, for composite steel and concrete floors, the applied fire protection on a significant number of floor beams could be eliminated (11) due to the slab acting as a membrane (see *Fig. 4*). In the UK, this led to the development of a design guide that has been widely used in multi-storey buildings (12). Moreover, the methodology has been adopted internationally, including the joint Australian and New Zealand design standard for composite steel-concrete buildings AS/NZS 2327 (13).

Fig. 4. Cardington frame after fire test

Following subsequent research programmes extending and refining the methodology, a simple calculation method for composite floors under tensile membrane action is presented within a new Annex to prEN 1994-1-2.

5 FUTURE RESEARCH TASKS

5.1 Strain limited design of composite beams in bending

Similar to the existing relationship between the reduction factor β and z_{pl}/h given within the current Eurocode 4, the proposed rules in prEN 1994-1-1 have been developed based on cross-section analyses of composite beams, which have full shear connection (14). In the future, research on strain limited design of composite beams with partial shear connection would be valuable.

5.2 Punching shear of composite slabs

Historically, the rules for punching shear on composite slabs have been based on the provisions given in Eurocode 2. During the drafting of prEN 1994-1-1, very little experimental information on the performance of composite slabs when subjected to concentrated loads was found. Investigations that include concentrated load tests on composite slabs with different sheeting types would be helpful in developing an understanding of the different failure modes that can occur in practice.

5.3 Slim floor beams

In the development of the prEN 1994-1-1 rules, no information could be found on the rotation capacity of slim floor beams at plastic hinge positions. Therefore, when plastic global analysis is used, it is currently left to the designer to demonstrate whether sufficient rotation capacity exists. Future research investigating the rotation capacity of slim floor beams would be beneficial.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The present paper provides a selection of the changes that will be included within the second-generation of Eurocode 4. In addition, areas that are considered worthy of future research are presented. At the time of writing, the CEN Enquiry ballot for Eurocode 4 is underway. Following the CEN Formal Vote ballot, it is expected that the DAV for Eurocode 4 will be March 2026.

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